

Fertilizer management

Comparative efficiency of *Sesbania*, *Gliricidia*, and urea as N sources in wetland rice

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Sesbania cannabina is a well-recognized green manure (GM) for rice. Farmers have not widely adopted it because they are reluctant to use their land, water, and other inputs for raising a crop exclusively for GM. *Gliricidia sepium*, a perennial leguminous tree, is grown extensively in roadsides, hedges, and field boundaries in the tropics. High foliage yields, vigorous coppicing ability, and tolerance for regular lopping make *Gliricidia* a good GM. Using loppings for GM is popular in many parts of southern India.

We compared efficiency of *Sesbania*, *Gliricidia*, and urea as N sources for rice variety Rasi in a Vertisol with 0.92% organic C, 0.10% total N, and pH 7.9 during 1988 dry season (DS).

The equivalent of 100 kg N/ha from each source was supplied to rice crops. A no-N control was also used. Eight-wk-

old *Sesbania* plants (from a different field) and 1-m-long tender *Gliricidia* loppings (collected from hedges) were chopped into 10-15 cm pieces for incorporation into the puddled field as a single basal dose at 2 d before transplanting. On a fresh weight basis, the *Sesbania* samples contained 0.50% total N, and the *Gliricidia*, 0.64% total N. Urea was applied in two equal splits at transplanting and 57 d later at panicle initiation (PI) stage. The 2 M KCl extractable $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ in soil under the different N treatments was monitored through the first 8 wk after transplanting (WAT). Rice grain yield and total N uptake at PI and at maturity were evaluated.

Urea was the most efficient of the N sources. Efficiency of *Gliricidia* N and *Sesbania* N was about 67% and 45%, respectively, that of urea N. Crop N uptake from *Gliricidia* was significantly higher than from *Sesbania* at both PI and maturity. Rice yield using *Gliricidia* was 0.6 t/ha more than with *Sesbania*.

Gliricidia released relatively more N to the soil than *Sesbania* through 8 WAT.

While the rice crop was growing, mean available N content in the soil (0-15 cm plow layer) treated with *Gliricidia* was 16.6 kg/ha and 13.9 kg/ha with *Sesbania*. Availability of N to the rice crop from *Gliricidia* at early tillering stage (4 WAT) was significantly higher than that from *Sesbania* (see table).

Gliricidia seems to be more promising than *Sesbania* as a GM source of N for wetland rice. ■

Efficiency of 3 N sources in rice variety Rasi in a submerged Vertisol. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India, 1988 DS.

N source	Available N ^a content in soil (kg/ha)						N uptake by rice (kg/ha)		Rice grain yield (t/ha)
	Days after transplanting						PI	Maturity	
	2	7	14	28	42	56			
None	10.9	13.4	13.4	7.5	7.4	1.3	49.4	69.0	3.9
Urea ^b	46.8	42.2	39.1	17.0	3.8	2.7	91.6	146.0	6.6
<i>Sesbania</i>	20.1	20.5	20.7	15.2	4.7	2.1	70.9	102.1	5.1
<i>Gliricidia</i>	18.6	22.2	22.2	29.2	4.8	2.7	87.0	114.2	5.7
LSD (0.05)	4.3	2.9	3.8	2.6	1.0	0.9	9.0	8.2	0.8

^a2 M KCl extractable $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ in 0-15 cm plow layer. ^bApplied in two equal splits at transplanting and 57 d later.

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Effect of lignite fly ash (LFA) on rice

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We evaluated the effect of LFA on dry matter production (DMP) of rice cultivar IR20 grown in a lateritic sandy clay loam soil in Kadampuliyur village, South Arcot District, TN, during Jun-Sep 1987 and Dec 1987-Apr 1988. Analysis of LFA (obtained from Thermal Power Plant, Neyveli, TN, India) indicated pH of 10, EC 1.0 dS/m, 49% SiO_2 , 12% CaO, 6.3% MgO, 8.3% K_2O , 300 ppm

available SiO_2 , and no N and P.

The experimental soil had pH 5.5, EC 0.1 dS/m, 0.17% organic C, 70 ppm available SiO_2 (low), 70 ppm available N (low), 2.8 ppm Olsen's P (low), and 83 ppm available K (low). Soil was air-dried, sieved, and put into clay pots at 10 kg/pot. In the first season, LFA was applied at 5 g/pot (1 t/ha). Nutrient treatments were N, NP, NK, and NPK, with and without LFA (Table 1). The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design with four replications.

Rainwater was added to the pots, which were then submerged for 10 d, We applied N as urea at 40 ppm, P as

Table 1. DMP and P and SiO_2 content of rice when LFA was applied in lateritic sandy clay loam soil.^a 1987.

Treatment	DMP (g/pot)	Nutrient content			
		P (ppm)	SiO_2 (%)		
N	11.07	c	295	e	3.09
N + LFA	11.36	c	350	c	3.95
N + P	13.39	bc	323	d	2.90
N + P + LFA	14.83	b	362	c	3.11
N + K	9.56	d	309	de	2.95
N + K + LFA	10.74	b	421	b	2.40
N + P + K	15.99	cd	328	d	3.16
N + P + K + LFA	22.70	a	569	a	2.86
LSD (P=0.05)	3.09		19		ns ^b

^aValues followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bns = not significant.

Table 2. Effect of LFA and added P on grain and straw yields of IR20 in lateritic sandy clay loam soil. 1988.

Treatment LFA (g/pot)	Yield			
	Grain (g/pot)	% increase	Straw (g/pot)	% increase
		<i>P</i> (0 ppm)		
No added LFA	16.29		20.47	
2.5	17.48	7.3	22.68	10.8
5.0	23.07	41.6	27.72	35.4
7.5	16.81	3.2	17.64	-13.8
Mean	18.81		22.12	
		<i>P</i> (13 ppm)		
No added LFA	17.25		25.08	
2.5	19.31	11.9	24.23	-3.4
5.0	23.62	36.9	33.40	33.2
7.5	16.07	-6.8	17.18	-31.5
Mean	19.06		24.97	
LSD (<i>P</i> = 0.05)				

diammonium phosphate at 13 ppm, and K as sulfate potash at 11 ppm.

Twenty-day-old rice seedlings raised in the experimental soil were transplanted at two seedlings per hill, three hills per

pot, and allowed to grow for 50 d under flooded condition.

LFA combined with NPK resulted in the highest DMP (22.7 g/pot), which was about 42% more than that of NPK alone

(Table 1). P content was consistently higher when LFA was added. LFA with N, P, K, and their combinations did not influence SiO₂ content in rice plants.

Another pot culture trial in Dec 1987-Apr 1988 incorporated 0, 2.5, 5.0, and 7.5 g LFA/pot (0, 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5 t/ha) with 13 ppm P and no P. The experiment was conducted using a completely randomized design with three replications. N at 40 ppm and K at 11 ppm were applied to all pots.

Regardless of P treatment, LFA at 5 g/pot gave the highest grain yield, followed by LFA at 2.5 g/pot (Table 2). Applying P with LFA at 2.5 g/pot increased grain yield, but at 7.5 g LFA/pot, yields were reduced by 6.8% compared with no LFA.

Straw yield was markedly increased with 5 g LFA/pot with or without P. LFA at 7.5 g/pot adversely affected straw yield.

Silicicolous plants, such as rice, can benefit from up to 1 t LFA/ha, particularly in lateritic acid soils. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Using desiccation to preserve blue-green algae (BGA)

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We wanted to find a suitable method to preserve BGA in the dry state as an alternative to frequent subculturing of fresh cultures. We produced soil-based cultures, cultures deposited on paper strips, and mass cultures and tested their viabilities after long storage.

Soil-based cultures were produced in 250-ml erlenmeyer flasks or on petri plates (14 cm diam). A loopful of culture was inoculated into a previously autoclaved mixture of 100 ml BG-11₀ medium and 20 g soil. Cultures were incubated under continuous illumination for 4 wk and then dried slowly. Cultures were ground and kept in plastic bottles at room temperature.

To preserve strains on paper, 6- to 12-wk-old liquid cultures were deposited aseptically on to sterile strips (2 × 7.8 cm)

of Whatman chromatography paper no. 3 and dried in a convection flow clean bench. Paper strips were stored in plastic bags at room temperature.

Mass cultures were produced in 12 liters of medium exposed to continuous illumination, stirring, and bubbling of an air-CO₂ mixture. Cultures were decanted and centrifuged after 4-6 wk of growth. They were dried slowly under fluorescent lamps and later ground and stored in plastic bottles.

Viabilities of the dried cultures were tested by incubating aliquot parts of the soil-based and mass cultures in 25-ml erlenmeyer flasks containing 5 ml of medium. For cultures on paper strips, 0.5-cm portions were cut and incubated like the other cultures.

Of the 65 soil-based cultures, 58 remained viable after 6 yr of storage. A disadvantage of using soil as a base is the presence of contaminants. About 40% of the cultures were contaminated with either diatoms, BGA (notably *Nostoc* sp.), or both. Soil must be sterilized completely to remove indigenous flora when using this preservation method.

Fifteen of the 136 strains dried on paper strips lost viability after at least 5 mo of storage. The number increased to 30 after another 6 mo, and none of the strains were viable after 4 yr. The paper strip method should only be used for short-term preservation.

Powdered mass cultures remained viable after 9 yr of storage. As with the soil-based cultures, the populations decreased tremendously over time; higher aliquot parts and longer incubation periods were required to obtain growth. The best method for preserving BGA in the dry state is the powdered mass culture, which has the advantages of unialgality and retention of viability for up to 9 yr. ■

Effects of *Sesbania aculeata* (dhaincha) on rice yield

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We studied how rice yields were affected by green manuring with dhaincha and by incorporating green manure (GM) with graded doses of N, P, K, and Zn (see table).